

Highlights

Basic Harm Reduction data: C-EHRN
2025 monitoring report

42 European cities reported uneven availability of basic HR services:

Availability did not always translate into access:

OAT 37/40

Cities reported access restrictions

Naloxone 16/26

Cities reported access restrictions

Trends in availability 2020-2025

→ OAT and NSP remained stable and widely available in most cities.

→ Safer smoking kits, safer intranasal kits and naloxone fluctuated over time.

→ 3 cities reported the opening of drug consumption rooms.

Services needed to respond to emerging drug trends remain among the least available and least stable harm reduction interventions. As drug trends evolve, harm reduction services must evolve with them.

Correlation

European Harm Reduction Network

Basic Harm Reduction in Europe Service Provision in a Changing Drug Landscape

Civil Society Monitoring of
Harm Reduction in Europe 2025

Correlation

 European Harm
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Availability of basic harm reduction services remains uneven

Across the 42 reporting cities, some basic harm reduction services are widely available. Opioid agonist treatment (OAT), needle and syringe programmes (NSP), and harm reduction education are **reported in almost all cities**, indicating a strong baseline of service provision.

Other services are reported less frequently. Safer smoking materials and take-home naloxone are available in a majority of cities, but not all. Safer intranasal materials and drug checking services show more limited coverage, and drug consumption rooms remain the least commonly available service.

This distribution of services (figure 1) **raises questions about whether harm reduction systems are adapting quickly enough to a changing drug landscape**. Across Europe, stimulant use has increased, new psychoactive substances continue to emerge, and non-injecting routes of administration have become increasingly common [1,2,3,4]. These developments create new health risks that may not be adequately addressed by harm reduction systems primarily designed around opioid use and injecting practices [2].

Availability of Basic Harm Reduction Services in 42 European Cities

Figure 1: Availability of basic harm reduction services across 42 European cities.

Basic harm reduction services must evolve to reflect current drug trends.

- Expand drug checking services in response to concerns about adulteration and drug quality [1,2].
- Increase availability of take-home naloxone in light of the emergence of synthetic opioids [2,3].
- Provide safer smoking and safer intranasal equipment, as smoking and snorting become increasingly common routes of administration [1].

Availability ≠ equal access

While basic harm reduction services are widely reported, an important question remains: can they be accessed in practice? Our monitoring data shows that **availability does not always translate into access**.

Figure 2: Reported restrictions to access opioid agonist treatment and take-home naloxone in 42 European cities

OAT access restrictions

OAT is widely available across 40 out of 42 reporting cities. However, availability does not necessarily translate into access.

Restrictions are reported in nearly all cities where OAT is available (Figure 2).

Reported restrictions include exclusion criteria related to documentation, health insurance, age, and substance use (**Figure 3**), suggesting that access is not always based solely on clinical need. This is particularly concerning given that OAT is considered an essential intervention for reducing overdose risk and other drug-related harms.

In addition, service-level factors further affect access and continuity of care. Reported barriers include waiting times, geographical limitations, treatment-related costs, and rules affecting continuity of care such as temporary suspension or permanent exclusion. While these measures may reflect legitimate safety considerations or responses to non-adherence, their widespread presence suggests that access to treatment can be interrupted or restricted for some groups.

Figure 3: Reported barriers and restrictions affecting access to opioid agonist treatment across 37 cities with available OAT services.

Take-home OAT is widely reported across cities, with 39 cities indicating that this option is available. However, access to take-home doses is often subject to programme conditions and stability criteria, meaning that **not all clients can benefit equally** from this form of treatment delivery. While such requirements may be intended to support safe prescribing, they can also limit flexibility and reduce access for individuals who may benefit most from reduced supervision and more person-centered models of care.

These restrictions go against European and International guidelines. They must be addressed to ensure improved access and continuity of care.

Remove eligibility conditions related to substance use.

→ Concurrent use of drugs must not lead to exclusions from OAT [5,6,7].

OAT should be low-threshold and affordable.

→ Administrative and structural barriers should be minimised to support timely entry and continuity of treatment. Waiting times and travel distance should not prevent people from accessing OAT, which should be available free of charge or at low cost [5,6].

Strengthen continuity of care

→ Suspension and expulsion from OAT should be minimised. De-escalation approaches should be prioritised over zero tolerance when handling aggression or other disruptive behaviour [8,9].

Ensure equitable and non-discriminatory access to OAT

→ Services must prevent discrimination based on personal characteristics, mental health problems or legal status [10,11,12].

Naloxone access barriers

Take-home naloxone was reported available in 26 cities, yet **access in practice remains restricted** by requirements such as the need for medical prescription (12), enrolment in an OAT programme (10), or possession of health insurance (9). These conditions indicate that access to naloxone is not always low-threshold and may depend on engagement with formal healthcare or treatment services.

Ensure unrestricted access to naloxone

→ People who use opioids or are likely to witness an overdose should have low-threshold access to take-home naloxone, a life-saving medication [2,3,13]. This access should not be affected by barriers related to health insurance, prescription requirements, or enrolment in treatment programmes [13,14].

Trends in basic harm reduction service availability (2020-2025)

Figure 4: Map showing locations of C-EHRN focal points participating in the 2025 monitoring or/ and 2020–2025 comparison.

Services needed for emerging drug trends were the least stable

Services such as safer smoking kits, safer intranasal kits and take-home naloxone did not remain stable over the monitoring period (2020–2025). Changes in availability were observed across participating cities, with **some cities introducing these services, others discontinuing them, and some later reintroducing them.**

Unlike OAT and NSP, which remained consistently available throughout the period and appear to form the backbone of harm reduction responses in many cities, these interventions appear less secure and more dependent on local priorities, funding, and implementation conditions.

This reinforces concerns about whether harm reduction is keeping up with changing patterns of drug use [1,2,3]. As these drug patterns diversify, basic harm reduction services **should become more established and widely available, not continue to appear and disappear across cities.**

Trends in availability of basic harm reduction services across 23 European cities (2020 to 2025)

Service	Available throughout 2020–2025	Never reported 2020–2025	Introduced during monitoring period	Discontinued during monitoring period	Reintroduced after discontinuation
Safer smoking kits	11	2	6	2	2
Safer intranasal kits	9	7	2	4	1
Take-home naloxone	11	5	2	3	2
Drug checking	7	6	4	3	3

Note: Values show the number of cities (n = 23) reporting each service. They do not represent the number of service sites or programmes. A city may report more than one service type. Within each service, cities are counted in only one category (e.g. available throughout, introduced, discontinued, or reintroduced).

Figure 5: Trends and stability of selected harm reduction services across 23 European cities (2020–2025).

OAT and NSP remained stable and available

OAT and NSP were **consistently available** throughout this monitoring period. OAT was reported in all 23 cities every year between 2020 and 2025. NSP was also reported in all 23 cities between 2020 and 2024, with only one change observed in 2025, when due to funding shortages, the service became unavailable in Tirana.

The consistent availability of OAT and NSP throughout the monitoring period highlights their **well-established role** within harm reduction. Compared with other interventions that fluctuated over time, these services appear to form the backbone of harm reduction responses in many European cities.

Availability of DCRs increased

An encouraging trend can be observed in the availability of drug consumption rooms (DCRs). Between the 2020 and 2025 monitoring rounds, the number of cities reporting a DCR **increased from 6/23 to 9/23**. This reflects developments reported up to the 2024 reference year, including new DCRs in Athens, Prague and Porto.

This increase suggests growing recognition of DCRs as an essential component of harm reduction responses. Despite this progress, DCRs remain the least available service among those monitored. This contrasts with a substantial body of evidence supporting their effectiveness and highlights the need for further expansion across Europe.

Highlight: Drug Consumption Rooms Work. It's Time to Expand Them.

✓ DCRs reduce overdose deaths, improve safer use, and increase access to health and social services, with no evidence of increased crime or drug use [2,15,16]

✓ Critical role in reaching people who are not engaged with other services, acting as low-threshold entry points into care [15,17]

✓ DCRs improve public safety, including reductions in public injecting and drug-related litter [16,18]

Despite this evidence, DCRs remain unevenly distributed across Europe, concentrated in a small number of Western European countries [19]. Legal barriers, political resistance and unstable funding continue to limit implementation and threaten the sustainability of existing services [18]:

→ **Expand DCRs in underserved regions by addressing legal and regulatory barriers and providing sustained political and financial support [20,21].**

→ **Protect existing DCRs from closure or service reduction caused by unstable funding or political resistance.**

→ **Debunk myths about DCRs to overcome resistance and support implementation [17]**

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